

WINE questionnaire

This questionnaire is part of the participatory science project [Winegrowers Integrated in Novel Experiments](#) (WINE) of researchers from ETH Zürich and Agroscope. The questionnaire will help us understand the state of current vineyard management practices, specifically soil management practices and cover crop usage, across Switzerland.

We will ask questions regarding your viticultural practices, as well as your motivations and opinions. Additionally we would like to learn about the characteristics and management of a **single** plot.

We only collect personal information if you choose to share your name and email address with us voluntarily, which will enable us to keep you updated on the progress of our project. This information will be stored on servers within Switzerland or Europe and deleted after the end of the project. All data will be analyzed without being linked to your identity and the geolocations blurred to ensure that they cannot be traced to an individual.

Thank you for contributing to this Citizen Science Project!

* Indicates required question

1. Would you like to take this survey? *

⌵ Dropdc

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

General questions

2. Which **red** wine varieties do you grow?

Check all that apply.

Pinot Noir / Blauburgunder

Merlot

Gamay

Gamaret

Garanoir

Syrah

Cornalin / Landroter

Humagne Rouge

Diolinoir

Cabernet Franc

Divico

Cabernet Sauvignon

Galotta

- Cabernet Jura
- Regent
- Cabernet Dorsa
- Ancellotta
- Malbec
- Dunkelfelder
- Zweigelt
- Dornfelder
- Dakapo
- Mara
- Maréchal Foch
- Carminoir
- Plant Robert
- Léon Millot
- Bondola
- VB Cal 1-28
- Servagnin
- Cabernet Cortis
- Cabernet Noir
- Blaufränkisch / Lemberger
- Marselan
- Isabella
- Prior
- Chambourcin
- Cabernet Soyhières
- Muscat Bleu
- Mondeuse Rouge
- VB Cal 1-36
- Nebbiolo
- Cabernet Cubin
- Cabernet Mitos
- Pinotage
- Other: _____

3. Which **white** wine varieties do you grow?

Check all that apply.

- Chasselas / Gutedel
- Müller-Thurgau / Riesling-Silvaner
- Chardonnay
- Sylvaner / Rhin
- Petite Arvine

- Pinot Gris / Malvoisie / Grauburgunder
- Savagnin Blanc
- Sauvignon Blanc
- Pinot Blanc / Weissburgunder
- Viognier
- Gewürztraminer
- Muscat / Muskateller
- Marsanne Blanche / Ermitage
- Amigne
- Doral
- Johanniter
- Solaris
- Rheinriesling
- Humagne Blanc
- Räschling
- Kerner
- Sauvignier Gris
- Aligoté
- Muscaris
- VB Cal 6-04
- Sauvignon Gris
- Chenin Blanc
- Seyval Blanc
- Charmont
- Completer
- Cabernet Blanc
- Divona
- Scheurebe
- Muscat Oliver
- Freisamer / Freiburger
- Muscat Ottonel
- Altesse
- Sauvignon Soyhières
- Roussanne
- Rèze
- Auxerrois
- Mondeuse Blanche
- Sémillon
- Bianca
- Other: _____

4. On how many plots do you grow grapevines on?

We consider a plot to be a unit of cultivation in one location, usually divided by boundaries and planted with a single cultivar.

5. Does your viticulture classify as:

Check all that apply.

conventional (IP, ÖLN)

organic (BioSuisse)

biodynamic (Demeter)

Other: _____

New varieties

6. If you would plant **new varieties**, which would that be?

7. Why would you choose these varieties?

Mark only one oval per row.

	Very important	Somewhat important	Less important	Not important at all
more appreciated by the consumer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
better suited for the location	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
cheaper to produce	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
produces higher quantities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
expected to deal better with climate change	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
expect reduced chemical input	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
financial assistance associated with this variety	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

8. Do you have any other motivations for planting new varieties that were not listed in the previous question?

Soil Characteristics and Quality

9. Are certain plots associated with a higher quality of wine?

⌵ Dropdc

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Not known

10. If so, what do you think are the reasons for that?

11. How is the wine of your vines produced?

Check all that apply.

Yourself

Outsource wine making

Sell the grapes

Other: _____

12. How strongly do you expect different soil types to influence the wine quality in your viticulture?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

No influence Large influence

Vineyard Health

13. How much do your plots differ in terms of disease incidence?

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

No differences Big differences

14. What characteristics do you think contribute to a high infection risk?

15. What characteristics do you think contribute to naturally more healthy vineyards?

Example vineyard

Please choose **a single plot that exemplifies how you manage most of your vineyards.**

16. Where is the plot located?

To get the coordinates:

1. In a new browser window, open [Google Maps](#).
 2. Right-click the place or area on the map. This will open a pop-up window. You can find your latitude and longitude in decimal format at the top.
 3. To copy the coordinates automatically, left click on the latitude and longitude.
-

17. Which variety is grown there?

⌵ Dropd

Mark only one oval.

- Aligoté
- Altesse
- Amigne
- Ancellotta
- Auxerrois
- Bianca
- Blaufränkisch / Lemberger
- Bondola
- Cabernet Blanc
- Cabernet Cortis
- Cabernet Cubin
- Cabernet Dorsa
- Cabernet Franc
- Cabernet Jura
- Cabernet Mitos
- Cabernet Noir
- Cabernet Sauvignon
- Cabernet Soyhières
- Carminoir
- Chambourcin
- Chardonnay
- Charmont
- Chasselas / Gutedel
- Chenin Blanc
- Completer

- Cornalin / Landroter
- Dakapo
- Diolinoir
- Divico
- Divona
- Doral
- Dornfelder
- Dunkelfelder
- Freisamer / Freiburger
- Galotta
- Gamaret
- Gamay
- Garanoir
- Gewürztraminer
- Humagne Blanc
- Humagne Rouge
- Isabella
- Johanniter
- Kerner
- Léon Millot
- Malbec
- Mara
- Maréchal Foch
- Marsanne Blanche / Ermitage
- Marselan
- Merlot
- Mondeuse Blanche
- Mondeuse Rouge
- Müller-Thurgau / Riesling-Silvaner
- Muscaris
- Muscat / Muskateller
- Muscat Bleu
- Muscat Oliver
- Muscat Ottonel
- Nebbiolo
- Petite Arvine

- Pinot Blanc / Weissburgunder
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- Pinot Noir / Blauburgunder
- Pinotage
- Plant Robert
- Prior
- Räschling
- Regent
- Rèze
- Rheinriesling
- Roussanne
- Sauvignon Blanc
- Sauvignon Gris
- Sauvignon Soyhières
- Savagnin Blanc
- Scheurebe
- Sémillon
- Servagnin
- Seyval Blanc
- Solaris
- Souvignier Gris
- Sylvaner / Rhin
- Syrah
- VB Cal 1-28
- VB Cal 1-36
- VB Cal 6-04
- Viognier
- Zweigelt
- Other

18. What clonal variety?

19. Which rootstock is the variety grafted on?

Mark only one oval.

- SO4
- 41B
- 3309C
- Kober 5BB
- Riparia Gloire
- 8B
- Fercal
- Other

20. What does the vineyard surrounding area look like?

Please select Side A as the **northernmost** side of the plot.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Forrest	Vineyards	Housing	Roads	Other agricultural land
Side A	<input type="radio"/>				
Side B	<input type="radio"/>				
Side C	<input type="radio"/>				
Side D	<input type="radio"/>				

21. What is the age of the vines planted on this plot?

in years

22. Estimate the root depth of the vines:

⌵ Dropdc

Mark only one oval.

< 1 m

1-2 m

> 2 m

Not known

23. Estimate the soil water reserves:

⌵ Dropdc

Mark only one oval.

low (< 100 mm)

medium (100-150 mm)

high (> 150 mm)

Not known

24. What is the approximate size of this plot?
in hectares

25. What is the trellis type used in this plot?

Check all that apply.

Halbbogen

Pendelbogen

Mosel loop

Guyot

Bush / Gobelet

Midwire Cordon

Lenz Moser

Other: _____

26. How is the soil managed **between the rows**?

Check all that apply.

- Bare soil with herbicide use
- Bare soil with mechanical tillage
- Spontaneous cover crops
- Seeded cover crops
- Mulching
- Other: _____

27. How is the soil managed **under the vines**?

Check all that apply.

- Bare soil with herbicide use
- Bare soil with mechanical tillage
- Spontaneous cover crops
- Seeded cover crops
- Mulching
- Other: _____

28. How do you fertilise the crop?

Check all that apply.

- No fertilisation
- Synthetic Fertiliser (N, P, K...)
- Compost
- Manure
- Other: _____

29. How often do you measure the nutrient contents of your soils?

⌵ Dropdc

Mark only one oval.

- never
- less than every 10 years
- every 5 - 10 years
- every 3 - 5 years
- every 3 - 1 years
- every year

30. Do you observe any nutrient deficiencies on the leaves?

⌵ Dropdc

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Not known

31. If yes, which nutrient deficiencies on leaves do you observe?

Check all that apply.

- nitrogen deficiency
- magnesium deficiency
- ferric chlorosis
- Other: _____

32. Please estimate the amount of nitrogen applied per year (kg / hectar / year):

⌵ Dropdc

Mark only one oval.

- < 10 kg / ha / year
- 10 - 30 kg / ha / year
- 30 - 50 kg / ha / year
- > 50 kg / ha / year

33. Please specify what other fertiliser and how much thereof you applied:

34. What is your water management strategy?

Check all that apply.

No irrigation

Drip Irrigation

Spray Irrigation

Other: _____

35. What is your disease management strategy?

Check all that apply.

Synthetic Fungicides

Organic Fungicides

Synthetic Insecticides

Organic Insecticides

Other: _____

36. What is the soil texture in this plot?

Mark only one oval per row.

	0 %	10 %	20 %	30 %	40 %	50 %	60 %	70 %	80 %	90
Clay	<input type="radio"/>									
Silt	<input type="radio"/>									
Sand	<input type="radio"/>									

Contact information

If you would like to receive information about the progress of this citizen science project please share your contact details!

37. What's your name?

38. What's your email address?

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